

Obstructive Sleep Apnoea - Aetiology, Diagnosis and Orthodontic Management.

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Abstract:

Patients with obstructive sleep apnoea syndrome (OSAs), a respiratory sleep disease, experience significant health and quality of life implications. Orthodontists should be aware of the symptoms and indicators of this condition and be able to give surgical, orthodontic, or orthopaedic correction of jaws⁶. A chronic history of loud snoring, daytime fatigue, daytime sleepiness, headaches upon waking or awakening, poor memory, personality changes, breathless awakenings, limb jerkiness, observed sleep disruption events, gasping and shortness of breath, and laboured noisy breathing are all indicators and symptoms of obstructive sleep apnoea⁸. In an effort to improve airflow, the patient may experience several apnoea episodes in a matter of minutes, waking them from their sleep. In addition to resulting in insufficient sleep duration, this also lowers the quality of sleep. This article focuses on the orthodontist's role in diagnosis and orthodontic treatment planning of OSA.

KEYWORDS: *Obstructive sleep apnoea syndrome (OSAS), Mandibular Advancement Devices (MADs), Polysomnography*

Introduction:

Obstructive sleep apnoea (OSA) is a type of sleep disorder marked by recurrent upper airway constriction and collapsing those results in periods of shallow or irregular breathing patterns (hypopnea) or breathing cessation (apnoea)⁶. In individuals with severe manifestations of the condition, blood oxygen levels drop quickly and decrease by 50% or more during partial or total breathing pauses that last for at least 10 seconds during sleep⁶. Increasingly, OSA is being recognised as a public health concern that calls for prompt diagnosis and appropriate treatment⁶. This condition is characterised by excessive sleeplessness, daytime drowsiness, chronic snoring, and cognitive impairment. Nighttime symptoms include witnessed apnoea, snoring, restless sleep, gasping and choking sensations and nocturia. Sleep apnoea leads to excessive daytime sleepiness because of sleep fragmentation and hypoxia, decreasing the quality of the sleep. This causes poor performance at work or school, cognitive impairment and depression².

Pathophysiology:

It has been suggested that the genioglossus muscle, a tongue muscle, is impaired in function in people with OSA. This results in the tongue prolapsing against the posterior pharyngeal wall during inspiratory effort during sleep. During sleep, the pharyngeal wall invaginates and the airway occludes. Air flow resistance from obstructions in the nasal cavity increases inspiration effort and the negative pressure in the pharyngeal wall airway. There is a greater likelihood of pharyngeal airway collapse with this suction.

Aetiology:

Obstruction of the upper airway during sleep can result from anatomical craniofacial and skeletal abnormalities. A direct cause of OSA in both children and adults has been identified as either maxillary or mandibular retrognathism, increased lower facial height, large tongue, elongated soft palate, or an inferiorly positioned

hyoid bone. The most prevalent skeletal condition that predisposes people to OSA is a mandibular deficit, which causes the tongue, soft palate, and soft tissues around the upper airway to shift posteriorly and constrict the upper airways.⁶

Risk Factors:

Obesity (upper body adiposity).

Mandibular or maxillary hypoplasia (Craniofacial anomalies).

Increased pharyngeal soft or lymphoid tissue Thickness

Tonsillar hypertrophy.

Nasal obstruction (rhinitis, septal deviation).

Endocrine abnormalities (hypothyroidism, acromegaly).

Hereditary (family history of OSA).

Smoking.

Alcohol consumption.

Menopause. (6)

Macroglossia

Upper airway tumours (rare) (4)

Signs and symptoms:

- Loud snoring
- Behavioural disturbances
- daytime drowsiness
- restless sleep,
- gasping and choking sensations
- Fragmentation of sleep
- Nocturnal cerebral hypoxia
- Excessive day time sleepiness
- Intellectual impairment.
- Memory loss.
- Impotence in men. 4
- Bruxism (nocturnal tooth grinding)
- Nocturnal and daytime enuresis
- Neck hyper extension
- Growth failure restriction
- Mouth breathing, causing dryness in mouth
- Chronic nasal congestion
- walking during sleep
- Fatigue
- Mood changes; irritability, frustration,
- impatience, depression, anxiety.
- Aggression and hyperactivity
- Poor school performance
- Poor concentration, and distraction
- Infraorbital venous congestion

Techniques for Determining the Level of Respiratory obstruction:

The methods are thorough history and physical examination:

- Sleeping habits
- Snoring
- Mouth breathing habits
- Headaches
- Hypersomnia
- Lethargy
- Gained weight.
- Difficulty in awakening.

Diagnosis:

The diagnosis of OSA can be made by the following ways:

- Sleep history
- Polysomnography (PSG): Gold Standard test for diagnosis.
- Apnoea hypopnea index (AHI)
- Epworth sleepiness scale questionnaire (ESS)

Polysomnography:

Polysomnography is considered as golden standard for the diagnosis of sleep apnoea. The study involves an overnight stay in the laboratory accompanied by multichannel monitoring or numerous physiologic variables under constant observation by a technician. Throughout the investigation, sleep phases and consistency, breathing exertion, airflow, oxygen saturation, and body position, electrocardiogram, and movements are recorded.

- **Apnea hypopnea index (AHI)**

TABLE 1

Apnea hypopnea index SCORE CLASSIFICATION FOR ADULTS	
APNOEA SEVERITY	Apnea hypopnea index (AHI) EVENTS/HOUR OF SLEEP
NORMAL	<5
MILD	$5 \leq \text{AHI} < 15$
MODERATE	$15 \leq \text{AHI} < 30$
SEVERE	≥ 30

TABLE 2

Epworth sleepiness scale questionnaire (ESS)

EPWORTH SLEEPINESS SCALE (ESS)				
What is your total score from the Epworth Sleepiness Scale? Choose 1 if score is 0-6 3 if score is 11-13 2 if score is 7-10 4 if score is >14				
Situation	0 (no dozing)	1 (slight chance of dozing)	2 (Moderate chance of dozing)	3 (High chance of dozing)
Sitting and Reading	0	1	2	3
Watching Television	0	1	2	3
Sitting inactive in a public place	0	1	2	3
Lying down to rest in afternoon	0	1	2	3
Sitting to talking to someone	0	1	2	3
Sitting quietly after lunch	0	1	2	3
In a car, white stopped In traffic	0	1	2	3
	Total score:			

TREATMENT OF OBSTRUCTIVE SLEEP APNOEA:

Obstructive sleep apnoea treatment

Options for treatment can be roughly categorised as follows:

1. Behavioural interventions
2. Treatment Options without surgery
3. Treatment Options with surgery.

Behavioural interventions:

Since weight loss therapy reduces symptoms of OSAHS and other linked conditions, persons with obstructive sleep apnoea should be encouraged to do so as they are obese. For their overall health, smokers should be counselled to quit. Drugs, sleeping pills, and alcohol should all be avoided as they may impair airway dilator function and exacerbate OSAHS. Patients with mild OSA are candidates for positional treatment. In order to reduce symptoms, patients should be told not to sleep on their backs and to raise the head of the bed.

Non-surgical interventions

a) **Continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP):**

For moderate to severe OSA, CPAP is the recommended course of treatment. A new device called a continuous positive airway pressure machine has a mask that fits securely over the patient's nose. It maintains the neck open all night long and transmits a constant flow of air.

Similar to a pneumatic splint, continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) maintains the airway open while you sleep. It functions by using a flow generator to supply positive pressure to the patient's wearing nasal mask via an airline. This airflow creation maintains the airway open, avoids breathing pauses, and returns oxygen levels to normal. Modern CPAP machines are lightweight, relatively compact, and come in a range of mask sizes for a proper fit.

Although they are uncommon, significant epistaxis and paranasal sinusitis are two of the main side effects of CPAP.

b) **Oral appliance therapy:**

Orthodontic appliances should be made such that, depending on the patient's condition, they can be worn permanently or detachable. These devices open up the lower pharynx, push the tongue and mandible forward, and enable constant breathing as you sleep. Mandibular advancement appliances (MAA) and tongue retention devices (TRD) are two examples.

c) **Surgical interventions:**

When noninvasive treatments like CPAP and oral devices have failed, surgery may be considered. It is performed when there is an anatomical defect that may be fixed in the future to resolve the breathing issues. It solves the issue by reducing tissue from the tongue, adenoids, tonsils, uvula, and soft palate.

1. Uvulopalatopharyngoplasty (UPPP): This procedure reconstructs the throat by excising the undesired mucosa on the pharyngeal walls and the posterior edges of the soft palate.

2. Adenotonsillectomy: The most popular treatment for kids with OSA is the surgical excision of the tonsils and adenoids.

3. Tracheostomy: Tracheostomy totally avoids the blockage and was the first surgical treatment for OSAHS.

Other surgical techniques:

1. Bariatric (weight-reducing) surgery: For some people, losing weight is an effective treatment for OSAHS, because weight affects how severe OSAHS is.

2. Nasal surgery: This procedure lowers nasal airflow resistance, lowers nasal pressure, and enhances nasal CPAP compliance.

Management in adult patients:

For treating OSA, continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) therapy is the gold standard and is considered as first treatment option for moderate to severe sleep apnoea patients. It is the most effective in eliminating obstructive breathing events and improving nocturnal oxygen saturation. To treat OSA, continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) is frequently used to preserve upper airway patency during sleep by delivering a constant airway pressure during inspiration and expiration. However, side effects include discomfort, pressure

intolerance, claustrophobia, skin irritations or lesions from the mask, mouth dryness, or nasal symptoms (congestion, dryness, and epistaxis) because of which most patients stop their therapy ⁶.

Oral Appliance Therapy:

As an alternative to continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP), a variety of oral appliances (OAs) have been utilised with the aim of maintaining upper airway patency during sleep by altering upper airway configuration and enlarging the pharyngeal lumen. OAs aim to correct the posterior position of the tongue and the mandible which tend to fall posteriorly during the supine position as a result of gravity.

The indications for OAs:

- Individuals with moderate to mild OSAs.
- Individuals who snore on a regular basis (without SA).
- Individuals who had attempted CPAP treatment but failed.
- Individuals who declined tracheostomy, tonsillectomy, adenoidectomy, or craniofacial surgery.
- In combination with CPAP devices to help in reducing the patient's AHI in order to achieve more tolerable air pressure settings.⁶

The advantages of OAs are the following:

- more comfortable than CPAP therapy.
- Less side effects as compared to CPAP
- Involves less equipment and therefore easier to travel with.

Mandibular advancement devices (MADs):

Simple delivery, low bulk, lip seal maintenance, enough tongue space, non-interference with sleep, low cost, and lateral freedom are the ideal characteristics of removable appliances.⁴ During sleep, MADs keep the mandible stable in a forward position to preserve a clear airway.⁶ The lower jaw and tongue are held protruding during sleep by maxillary and mandibular splints, which open the airway, allowing regular breathing, and provide immediate comfort.⁶

CONCLUSIONS:

The most common symptoms of apnoea are loud snoring, breathing pauses, and occasionally noticeable arm and body movements. The victim may wake up unexpectedly sweating, gasping for oxygen, or experiencing choking feelings. Additional symptoms could include elevated blood pressure, cognitive issues, inability to focus, and repeated naps during the day, particularly in inappropriate settings (such as meetings or while driving). Diagnosis might be challenging because many of these symptoms can potentially be caused by a variety of other diseases. Anatomical conditions that may contribute to this issue may be found by orthodontic diagnosis. A lateral cephalometric radiograph showing enlarged tonsils or adenoids, or On a P-A radiograph, a narrow nasal cavity and a maxillary width deficit are signs that the patient should be questioned about other symptoms. It is necessary to see a doctor if obstructive sleep apnoea is suspected.

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